

Safety Rod Reactivity Worth in the Advanced Test Reactor

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ABSTRACT

This work discusses expected Safety Rod worth and margin of subcriticality for the Advanced Test Reactor (ATR). The safety basis for ATR is approved by the United States Department of Energy and requires a minimum reactivity worth of Safety Rods for each operating cycle, including an assumption that no more than one operable Safety Rod fails to insert when a scram is executed. Necessary reactivity worths have historically been predicted with simple correlations. The MC21 neutronics code has been validated against measurement data to directly give an explicit core reactivity worth for desired shutdown scenarios. These explicit calculations reduce the uncertainty inherent in previously used correlations.

Keywords: Advanced Test Reactor, ATR, Safety Rod, Reactivity Worth

1. INTRODUCTION

The ATR core (see Figure 1) consists of forty (40) plate-type fuel elements, of aluminum-clad highly-enriched uranium. Pressurized water is both the moderator and the primary coolant and flows downward through the fuel element channels. The forty elements are organized around nine (9) flux traps, and power is shifted radially and azimuthally by means of control elements such as outer shim control cylinders, in order to obtain desired powers for irradiation of flux trap experiments. The purpose of localized power control is to simultaneously irradiate multiple experiments in the various flux traps, at programmable power levels. Most of the flux traps include the additional advantage of an in-pile tube, isolated from the reactor primary coolant system, which allows a given experiment to be irradiated at temperature, pressure, and chemistry conditions selected by the sponsor [1].

For convenience, fuel elements are grouped into five lobes, named for the Center (C) and for the intercardinal directions in each corner (Northwest (NW), Northeast (NE), Southwest (SW), and Southeast (SE)). The C lobe is in some contexts divided into fourths, allowing the ATR core to be grouped into four quadrants (NW, NE, SW, and SE). Each lobe contains a flux trap. The four other flux traps are known as outer flux traps, for being outside the closed fuel serpentine, and are designated by cardinal directions (North (N), West (W), East (E), and South (S)). Power is said to be produced by each lobe or quadrant and is indicated to operators. Outer flux trap powers are also indicated, as the average of the C lobe and the two adjacent corner lobes.

Fuel is loaded as a combination of fresh and re-used elements. Generally, for a longer cycle or higher powers, more fresh fuel elements are required. Normally, fresh fuel contains some ¹⁰B loading, to decrease power peaking in selected plate locations. However, non-borated fuel is available for certain cycle designs where additional fuel reactivity is desired. As the beryllium reflector ages, another available fuel design has no fuel in the outermost plate, reducing flux right next to the reflector.

Figure 1. Plan View of ATR Core.

As indicated in Figure 1, Outer Shim Control Cylinders (OSCCs) are withdrawn by rotating such that the hafnium plate is moved further from the fuel. In addition to providing localized control for each corner lobe, the axial shape of the neutron flux is largely unperturbed. Safety Rods are not indicated in the Legend of Figure 1 but are annular and occupy space between driver fuel and the flux trap in six locations: N, W, E, SW, S, and SE. Figure 1 shows that each Safety Rod consists of four (4) absorber plates (hafnium) to cover the azimuthal distance.

ATR core power is limited to 250 Megawatts (MW). Individual lobe power is limited to 60 MW. Most cycles operate with lobe powers of 18-25 MW and total core power near 110 MW.

The MC21 code [2] has been used extensively to analyze ATR [3-4] and is used here to reduce conservatism in the legacy SUPRMAX code [5]. Fundamentally, MC21 can explicitly calculate the reactivity worth for full insertion of a desired number of Safety Rods, while SUPRMAX is based on a summation of individual rod insertions pulled from correlations. SUPRMAX does not adjust for effects of Safety Rods on each other, such as shadowing or otherwise shifting power from one lobe to another.

2. MODEL BENCHMARKS AGAINST MEASURED SAFETY ROD WORTH

The most recent Safety Rod worth measurements were made in 2022 [6] and were used to benchmark models. Measurements are made by incrementally inserting one Safety Rod in small steps and computing core reactivity from indicated reactor period. Prior to full insertion of the Safety Rod, core reactivity worth in ATR is so low as to lose the neutron population before an indication can be obtained; therefore, the worth of a full Safety Rod is found by extrapolation from successful measurement steps.

At each measurement step, two competing contributions to the measurement uncertainty are

- 1) The drift in indicated core reactivity worth, which exacerbates with departure from level reactor power and therefore with Safety Rod insertion
- 2) The relative sizes of deliberate and uncontrolled contributions to core reactivity worth, which improves with larger deliberate insertion of negative reactivity and therefore with Safety Rod insertion

As a result of the above, the best measurement for each Safety Rod is the furthest insertion at which a steady reactor period is observed.

To determine the statistical significance of drift in indicated reactivity worth with time (addressing criterion 1) above), a sample Pearson correlation coefficient was determined at each measurement step (Equation (1)).

$$r = \frac{\sum_{x=1}^n (x_i - \bar{x}) \cdot (y_i - \bar{y})}{\sqrt{\sum_{x=1}^n (x_i - \bar{x})^2} \times \sqrt{\sum_{x=1}^n (y_i - \bar{y})^2}} \quad (1)$$

Where

r is the Pearson correlation coefficient

n is the number of data used at each measurement step; 50 evenly spaced data points were used in this work

x_i is the time at each datum

\bar{x} is the average time value for data representing each step

y_i is the indicated core reactivity worth at each datum

\bar{y} is the average indicated core reactivity worth for data representing each step

The expected model bias for each Safety Rod is labeled on *Figure 2*. As described in Appendix C, each expected bias is based on one measurement step, chosen based on the quality of the specific measurement. These modeling errors do not correlate with relative power or with height of the partially inserted Safety Rod; therefore, each is taken as an independent estimate of the true modeling bias for any Safety Rod, with the assumption that the measured data is accurate.

Based on data on *Figure 2*, the expected bias is 11.11%. With 95% confidence, a 14.88% bias is conservative. With 99% confidence, a 17.40% bias is conservative.

Figure 2. Model Overestimation for each Safety Rod.

3. SAFETY ROD SCRAM WORTH RESULTS

Various cycle models were modified to find core reactivity worth with Safety Rods inserted. Consistent with the approved safety basis, each model was used once to show the worth of inserting all Safety Rods and once again for each Safety Rod stuck out. The results are easily distinguishable between cycles designed for higher powers in SW and SE lobes and all other cycles. The obvious reason is that without moment of control shims, the importance of various Safety Rods is driven by fuel loading, which is programmed every operating cycle to provide requested lobe powers. By design, the highest test powers are planned in flux traps that also contain a Safety Rod.

The reactivity worth difference between two states is found per Equation (2)(1).

$$\Delta\rho = \rho_2 - \rho_1 = \frac{k_2 - 1}{k_2 \cdot \beta} - \frac{k_1 - 1}{k_1 \cdot \beta} = \frac{k_2 - k_1}{k_2 \cdot k_1 \cdot \beta} \quad (2)$$

Where

$\Delta\rho$ is the difference in reactivity worth

ρ_1 and ρ_2 are the reactivity worth of each state relative to exact criticality

k_1 and k_2 are the neutron multiplication factors at each state

β is the effective delayed neutron fraction

3.1. Results for Most Cycles (All Lobes < 47 Megawatts (MW))

Table I shows the immediate reactivity worth for inserting Safety Rods (with indicated rods sticking out) at various times in the duration of three recent cycles. All three cycles were designed for all lobes < 47 MW. The average and sample standard deviation are also shown for each column, to quantify the data spread.

Table I. Scram worth, with designated Safety Rod stuck out.

	Timestep	None	N	W	E	SW	S	SE
A	1	-20.999\$	-13.800\$	-15.750\$	-17.470\$	-18.230\$	-18.494\$	-18.919\$
	2	-19.485\$	-12.803\$	-14.867\$	-16.365\$	-16.855\$	-17.528\$	-17.502\$
	3	-18.066\$	-12.096\$	-13.707\$	-15.973\$	-16.210\$	-16.782\$	-16.526\$
	4	-18.918\$	-12.529\$	-14.496\$	-16.083\$	-16.814\$	-17.290\$	-16.829\$
	5	-18.155\$	-11.962\$	-13.789\$	-15.736\$	-16.382\$	-16.704\$	-16.593\$
	6	-18.946\$	-12.854\$	-14.561\$	-16.485\$	-16.325\$	-17.327\$	-17.513\$
	7	-19.668\$	-13.239\$	-15.152\$	-16.899\$	-16.808\$	-17.808\$	-17.837\$
	8	-19.936\$	-13.283\$	-15.259\$	-16.892\$	-17.297\$	-17.826\$	-17.776\$
	9	-19.869\$	-13.348\$	-15.212\$	-16.897\$	-17.123\$	-17.691\$	-17.898\$
	10	-18.975\$	-12.916\$	-14.570\$	-16.524\$	-16.426\$	-17.100\$	-17.356\$
	11	-18.990\$	-12.922\$	-14.586\$	-16.388\$	-16.354\$	-17.080\$	-17.328\$
B	1	-21.077\$	-13.852\$	-15.895\$	-16.855\$	-18.668\$	-18.625\$	-19.269\$
	2	-18.567\$	-12.293\$	-14.410\$	-15.079\$	-16.635\$	-17.180\$	-17.004\$
	3	-17.533\$	-11.553\$	-13.463\$	-14.817\$	-15.698\$	-16.392\$	-16.359\$
	4	-17.291\$	-11.452\$	-13.375\$	-14.590\$	-15.790\$	-16.245\$	-16.099\$
	5	-17.557\$	-11.679\$	-13.669\$	-14.733\$	-15.802\$	-16.373\$	-16.415\$
	6	-18.335\$	-12.047\$	-14.211\$	-14.934\$	-16.229\$	-16.882\$	-16.903\$
	7	-18.826\$	-12.520\$	-14.714\$	-15.377\$	-16.556\$	-17.319\$	-17.235\$
	8	-18.844\$	-12.321\$	-14.610\$	-15.312\$	-16.700\$	-17.245\$	-17.128\$
	9	-18.800\$	-12.595\$	-14.621\$	-15.380\$	-16.682\$	-17.169\$	-17.294\$
	10	-19.156\$	-12.954\$	-14.931\$	-15.503\$	-16.998\$	-17.142\$	-17.026\$
C	1	-20.115\$	-13.394\$	-16.006\$	-15.898\$	-17.500\$	-18.179\$	-17.231\$
	2	-19.334\$	-12.723\$	-15.393\$	-15.515\$	-16.621\$	-17.732\$	-16.040\$
	3	-19.040\$	-12.545\$	-15.411\$	-15.207\$	-16.558\$	-17.662\$	-15.918\$
	4	-19.879\$	-13.226\$	-15.796\$	-16.007\$	-16.689\$	-18.087\$	-16.617\$
	5	-19.395\$	-12.782\$	-15.322\$	-15.821\$	-16.416\$	-17.844\$	-17.125\$
	6	-19.696\$	-13.024\$	-15.623\$	-15.980\$	-16.622\$	-18.020\$	-17.104\$
	7	-19.813\$	-13.097\$	-15.770\$	-16.010\$	-16.440\$	-18.274\$	-17.426\$
	8	-19.956\$	-13.170\$	-15.809\$	-16.263\$	-16.177\$	-18.286\$	-17.411\$
	9	-20.157\$	-13.451\$	-16.064\$	-16.315\$	-16.445\$	-18.379\$	-17.409\$
	10	-19.803\$	-13.044\$	-15.621\$	-16.160\$	-16.639\$	-18.175\$	-17.425\$
	11	-19.956\$	-13.230\$	-15.846\$	-16.230\$	-16.925\$	-18.100\$	-17.400\$
	12	-20.090\$	-13.500\$	-15.985\$	-16.333\$	-16.549\$	-18.069\$	-17.631\$
	13	-19.776\$	-13.374\$	-15.853\$	-16.105\$	-16.163\$	-17.939\$	-17.269\$
Average		-19.265\$	-12.811\$	-15.010\$	-15.945\$	-16.657\$	-17.557\$	-17.200\$
Standard Deviation		±0.901\$	±0.611\$	±0.802\$	±0.692\$	±0.601\$	±0.638\$	±0.699\$

3.2. Results for Cycles with SW and SE Lobes > 47 MW

Table II shows the immediate reactivity worth for inserting Safety Rods (with indicated rods sticking out) at various times in the duration of three recent cycles that were designed for high lobe powers in both the SW and SE lobes, both of which also contain Safety Rods. The average and sample standard deviation are also shown for each column, to quantify the data spread.

Table II. Scram worth, with designated Safety Rod stuck out.

	Timestep	None	N	W	E	SW	S	SE
A	1	-24.180\$	-18.578\$	-18.792\$	-19.556\$	-15.745\$	-21.056\$	-19.957\$
	2	-22.536\$	-17.015\$	-17.276\$	-18.695\$	-13.689\$	-20.005\$	-18.678\$
	3	-22.362\$	-16.903\$	-17.409\$	-18.475\$	-13.380\$	-19.989\$	-18.233\$
	4	-22.696\$	-17.137\$	-17.729\$	-18.655\$	-13.810\$	-20.256\$	-18.224\$
	5	-25.955\$	-21.495\$	-21.376\$	-20.743\$	-15.212\$	-21.946\$	-15.434\$
	6	-26.063\$	-21.373\$	-21.432\$	-20.619\$	-15.700\$	-22.111\$	-15.607\$
	7	-26.162\$	-21.259\$	-21.445\$	-20.433\$	-15.181\$	-21.967\$	-15.101\$
	8	-25.806\$	-21.027\$	-21.210\$	-20.221\$	-14.924\$	-21.955\$	-15.019\$
	9	-18.319\$	-12.116\$	-15.000\$	-13.577\$	-16.359\$	-17.272\$	-15.855\$
	10	-19.001\$	-12.495\$	-15.628\$	-13.831\$	-16.934\$	-17.850\$	-16.131\$
	11	-19.373\$	-12.772\$	-15.912\$	-14.068\$	-17.279\$	-18.060\$	-16.297\$
	12	-19.251\$	-12.790\$	-15.841\$	-14.150\$	-17.279\$	-18.068\$	-16.403\$
B	1	-25.611\$	-20.667\$	-21.792\$	-19.412\$	-17.344\$	-21.762\$	-16.666\$
	2	-25.097\$	-20.459\$	-21.403\$	-19.260\$	-16.015\$	-21.583\$	-15.551\$
	3	-25.112\$	-20.325\$	-21.467\$	-19.099\$	-15.882\$	-21.643\$	-15.008\$
	4	-24.993\$	-20.104\$	-21.466\$	-18.956\$	-16.127\$	-21.541\$	-14.771\$
	5	-26.875\$	-24.034\$	-23.054\$	-21.852\$	-14.111\$	-22.203\$	-14.012\$
	6	-27.849\$	-24.896\$	-23.608\$	-22.674\$	-15.372\$	-22.733\$	-15.358\$
	7	-27.572\$	-24.641\$	-23.410\$	-22.434\$	-15.017\$	-22.669\$	-15.156\$
	8	-27.390\$	-24.499\$	-23.455\$	-22.264\$	-14.963\$	-22.782\$	-14.635\$
	9	-27.344\$	-24.317\$	-23.187\$	-22.263\$	-14.642\$	-22.606\$	-14.518\$
	10	-27.289\$	-24.295\$	-23.306\$	-22.267\$	-14.230\$	-22.536\$	-14.276\$
	11	-27.224\$	-24.423\$	-23.373\$	-22.384\$	-14.455\$	-22.530\$	-14.492\$
	12	-27.453\$	-24.342\$	-23.168\$	-22.632\$	-14.078\$	-22.529\$	-15.494\$
C	1	-24.855\$	-20.141\$	-21.465\$	-19.088\$	-16.539\$	-21.348\$	-15.541\$
	2	-24.611\$	-19.625\$	-20.919\$	-19.006\$	-15.295\$	-21.195\$	-15.358\$
	3	-24.757\$	-20.186\$	-21.352\$	-19.293\$	-15.741\$	-21.324\$	-15.533\$
	4	-24.875\$	-20.187\$	-21.200\$	-19.348\$	-15.433\$	-21.224\$	-16.067\$
	5	-26.150\$	-22.670\$	-21.928\$	-21.818\$	-12.977\$	-21.891\$	-14.958\$
	6	-27.069\$	-23.458\$	-22.650\$	-22.172\$	-14.232\$	-22.415\$	-15.900\$
	7	-26.785\$	-23.286\$	-22.544\$	-22.146\$	-13.798\$	-22.265\$	-15.808\$
	8	-26.577\$	-23.083\$	-22.265\$	-22.033\$	-13.650\$	-22.276\$	-15.576\$
	9	-26.819\$	-23.356\$	-22.727\$	-21.899\$	-14.400\$	-22.303\$	-14.853\$
	10	-26.821\$	-23.221\$	-22.802\$	-21.861\$	-15.016\$	-22.346\$	-14.717\$
	11	-26.922\$	-23.348\$	-23.037\$	-21.377\$	-15.692\$	-22.119\$	-14.233\$
	12	-26.874\$	-23.525\$	-23.082\$	-21.584\$	-15.859\$	-22.143\$	-14.187\$
	13	-24.805\$	-19.243\$	-20.686\$	-19.376\$	-15.574\$	-21.383\$	-15.154\$
	14	-24.927\$	-19.433\$	-20.737\$	-19.518\$	-15.784\$	-21.514\$	-15.846\$
	15	-25.044\$	-19.541\$	-20.809\$	-19.535\$	-16.275\$	-21.539\$	-15.715\$
Average		-24.781\$	-20.045\$	-20.682\$	-19.562\$	-15.461\$	-21.238\$	-15.806\$
Standard Deviation		±2.582\$	±3.600\$	±2.444\$	±2.561\$	±1.087\$	±1.469\$	±1.166\$

4. CONCLUSIONS

After application of the biases discussed in Section 2, the bounding reactivity worth of 5 inserted Safety Rods is -10.088% at 95% confidence and -9.470% at 99% confidence, for a cycle designed for all lobes < 47 MW. For cycles designed for SW and SE lobes > 47 MW, the bounding SCRAM WORTH of 5 inserted Safety Rods is -11.684% at 95% confidence and -9.703% at 99% confidence. These values are less conservative than expected from SUPRMAX.

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